

European Open Research Repository User Survey 2026 - Results Report

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Authors	Lea GUGLIELMETTO CHALEARD (CERN)
Reviewer	Nicola TAROCCO
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Introduction

This report presents the results of the EU Open Research Repository (EOR) user feedback questionnaire conducted in April 2026 under the HORIZON-ZEN Plus project (Horizon Europe Grant nr. 101256740). In total 325 respondents completed the survey (representing 12.36% 325 / 2,629 – exceeding the initial target of 10%), which covered platform usage patterns, ease of use, FAIR data compliance priorities, AI/ML readiness, geospatial data needs, automated submission checks, and output visibility.

The survey was conducted on the EUSurvey platform, was fully anonymous, and participation was voluntary. This document presents quantitative results from the aggregate statistics.

Survey alias	Zenodo-EOR-Repository-Feedback-2026-03
Respondents	325 total responses
Survey period	April 2026
Platform	EUSurvey (anonymous, voluntary)

Statistics: Feedback Questionnaire for the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo

How often do you use your EU Project Community on Zenodo?

		Answers	Ratio
Often		111	34.15 %
Sometimes		136	41.85 %
Rarely		72	22.15 %
Never		6	1.85 %
No Answer		0	0 %

In which capacity are you answering this survey?

		Answers	Ratio
Researcher submitting outputs		207	63.69 %
Researcher using Zenodo records		71	21.85 %
Curator		125	38.46 %
Administrative manager		139	42.77 %
Other		14	4.31 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What types of data do you currently store in the EU repository?

		Answers	Ratio
Research papers		238	73.23 %
Datasets		198	60.92 %
Software		54	16.62 %
Deliverables or reports		216	66.46 %
Other		61	18.77 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How easy or difficult are the following tasks for you? : Uploading a dataset

		Answers	Ratio
Very difficult		2	0.62 %
Difficult	▬	11	3.38 %
Neutral	▬▬	56	17.23 %
Easy	▬▬▬▬	103	31.69 %
Very easy	▬▬▬▬▬	94	28.92 %
Not Applicable	▬▬▬	56	17.23 %
No Answer		3	0.92 %

How easy or difficult are the following tasks for you? : Providing grant/project information

		Answers	Ratio
Very difficult		2	0.62 %
Difficult	▬	22	6.77 %
Neutral	▬▬▬	51	15.69 %
Easy	▬▬▬▬▬▬▬▬	119	36.62 %
Very easy	▬▬▬▬▬▬▬	103	31.69 %
Not Applicable	▬▬▬	22	6.77 %
No Answer		6	1.85 %

How easy or difficult are the following tasks for you? : Validating data quality

		Answers	Ratio
Very difficult		6	1.85 %
Difficult		41	12.62 %
Neutral		78	24 %
Easy		50	15.38 %
Very easy		27	8.31 %
Not Applicable		115	35.38 %
No Answer		8	2.46 %

How easy or difficult are the following tasks for you? : Reviewing submissions

		Answers	Ratio
Very difficult		3	0.92 %
Difficult		9	2.77 %
Neutral		56	17.23 %
Easy		129	39.69 %
Very easy		88	27.08 %
Not Applicable		35	10.77 %
No Answer		5	1.54 %

How easy or difficult are the following tasks for you? : Creating a new project (new community)

		Answers	Ratio
Very difficult		2	0.62 %
Difficult		10	3.08 %
Neutral		45	13.85 %
Easy		130	40 %
Very easy		93	28.62 %
Not Applicable		34	10.46 %
No Answer		11	3.38 %

When submitting to the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo, how important are the following aspects, in particular when adhering to FAIR principles? (select all that apply)

		Answers	Ratio
Metadata requirements		239	73.54 %
Linking datasets and publications		240	73.85 %
Documentation requirements		165	50.77 %
Choosing appropriate licenses		196	60.31 %
File format requirements		111	34.15 %
I am not familiar with FAIR principles		20	6.15 %
Other		5	1.54 %
No Answer		0	0 %

If you work with ML/AI datasets, do you (or would you) use Zenodo to publish or discover datasets?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		113	34.77 %
No		212	65.23 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Which features would help make research outputs more usable for ML/AI systems or automated analysis?

		Answers	Ratio
Structured and high-quality metadata		55	16.92 %
Standardised file formats (e.g. CSV, Parquet, JSON, Arrow, image archives, WebDataset, Croissant)		51	15.69 %
Clear documentation and descriptions		63	19.38 %
Code snippets for how to use the dataset		27	8.31 %
Linking related outputs (datasets, software, publications)		33	10.15 %
Open and reusable licenses		29	8.92 %
APIs or programmatic access to data		19	5.85 %
I am not sure		16	4.92 %
Other		1	0.31 %
No Answer		212	65.23 %

Please rank which filtering options would be most useful when searching for ML/AI-ready datasets

	1	2	3	4	5	Score
Standardised file formats	14.15% 16	23.89% 27	39.82% 45	15.92% 18	6.19% 7	3.23 113
Modality (type of data, e.g. tabular, image, text,	28.31%	34.51%	14.15%	7.96%	15.04%	3.53

audio, video, geospatial)	32	39	16	9	17	113
Tasks (intended use case, e.g. image classification, object detection, text classification, speech recognition, time series forecasting)	39.82% 45	22.12% 25	16.81% 19	9.73% 11	11.5% 13	3.69 113
Number of citations, when available	13.27% 15	5.3% 6	13.27% 15	30.97% 35	37.16% 42	2.26 113
Most downloaded or most viewed	4.42% 5	14.15% 16	15.92% 18	35.39% 40	30.08% 34	2.27 113
No Answer	65.23 %					212

If you work with geospatial data, do you (or would you) use Zenodo to publish or discover research with geospatial metadata?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes		78	24 %
No		247	76 %
No Answer		0	0 %

What features or functionalities would you expect to see for Geo data in Zenodo when submitting or searching?

	1	2	3	4	Score
Map-assisted selection of an area or region	43.58% 34	28.2% 22	19.23% 15	8.97% 7	3.06 78
Free-text search for an area or region	17.94% 14	21.79% 17	23.07% 18	37.17% 29	2.2 78
Selection of geographic area or region from a list	25.64% 20	28.2% 22	28.2% 22	17.94% 14	2.61 78
Input of geospatial coordinates	12.82% 10	21.79% 17	29.48% 23	35.89% 28	2.11 78
No Answer	76 % 247				

Have automated checks helped you to review submissions faster?

		Answers	Ratio
Yes, significantly		56	17.23 %
Yes, somewhat		79	24.31 %
No noticeable difference		43	13.23 %
No, they made the process slower		1	0.31 %
I'm not aware of automated checks		146	44.92 %
No Answer		0	0 %

How do you feel about using AI to assist in some parts of the submission process? E.g. Field suggestions, automatic classification, etc.

		Answers	Ratio
Very negative		8	2.46 %
Negative		26	8 %
Neutral		113	34.77 %
Positive		145	44.62 %
Very positive		33	10.15 %
No Answer		0	0 %

To what extent has using Zenodo improved the visibility of your project outputs?

		Answers	Ratio
Not at all		16	4.92 %
Slightly		57	17.54 %
Moderately		127	39.08 %
Significantly		97	29.85 %
Very significantly		28	8.62 %
No Answer		0	0 %

Which features do you think would most improve the visibility of your outputs?

	1	2	3	4	Score
Ranking search results by most viewed/most downloaded	21.84% 71	33.53% 109	31.38% 102	13.23% 43	2.64 325
Displaying the number of citations	16.0% 52	24.3% 79	34.76% 113	24.92% 81	2.31 325
Search filter options by subjects or keywords	52.92% 172	24.3% 79	16.0% 52	6.76% 22	3.23 325
Easy way to search for ML/AI-ready datasets	9.23% 30	17.84% 58	17.84% 58	55.07% 179	1.81 325
No Answer	0 % 0				

Selected Open-Text Feedback

77 additional free-text feedback has been provided by the respondents, covering suggestions, praises, and criticisms. Below are representative themes with illustrative quotes.

1. Author Management and Metadata Entry

Author and contributor management is the most frequently cited pain point across the dataset:

"The procedure is very tedious, especially entering the authors one by one. What would help enormously: the researcher enters the DOI of the published paper, the form is filled automatically, and the researcher just needs to check and press submit."

"It would be great if everything could be automatically filled from the DOI. I never know which fields to complete and how."

"It would be good to have a simplified way to include authors — especially for publications where a lot of authors are present."

"The obligation to connect an ORCID to an author is sometimes limiting because it does not always apply."

2. Community Management

"For a large consortium project (an MSCA Doctoral Network), being able to sub-divide into work-package sub-pages would make management and overview much easier."

"Please make Communities metrics available, at least to owners."

"I would like to know more about the best way to create cluster-level communities to regroup multiple projects together with a single meta-community."

"I receive requests from people not involved in my project to accept submissions that have no connection with the project. Automated checks that could capture and reject these would help."

3. Data Management and Access

"We should be able to delete ourselves (if we are admins) publications, which will stop us from having to send an email to the support team and wait."

"I wanted to use Zenodo on other projects but the dataset size is a limitation. I can only use it with projects that have relatively small dataset sizes."

"A batch data/metadata upload facility would be helpful. Uploading one by one is very time consuming. EU-Farmbook has batch upload capacity; why not Zenodo?"

4. Positive Feedback

"You are doing great. Zenodo is the greatest invention. I have been using this consistently for some years and in several projects."

"You are doing an excellent job! I am so grateful Zenodo exists!"

"Thank you for your work — what you are doing is essential. Please continue."

"Zenodo has improved over the years and I've enjoyed watching it evolve. We appreciate the hard work that the Zenodo and OpenAIRE team have done."

Key Findings and Recommendations

The April 2026 survey confirms that the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo is well-regarded and actively used. The following priorities emerge from both the quantitative results and open-text responses:

#	Recommendation	Priority	Evidence
1	Implement metadata autofill from DOI/ORCID to reduce manual entry — the single most-requested improvement	High	Open text (many)
2	Improve search and filtering: subject/keyword facets ranked #1 for visibility improvement (score 3.23/4)	High	Section 8.2
3	Communicate automated checks proactively - 45% of users are unaware they exist	High	Section 7.1
4	Simplify author/contributor entry: retain names across sessions, support batch addition	High	Open text
5	Develop AI-assisted field suggestions with explicit opt-in controls (55% positive, but consent concerns raised)	Medium	Section 7.2
6	Add map-assisted geospatial selection (top-ranked geo feature, score 3.06/4)	Medium	Section 6.2
7	Enable ML/AI task/modality filters for dataset discovery (top-ranked by ML/AI users)	Medium	Section 5.3
8	Allow records to be added to a community post-submission without full resubmission	Medium	Open text
9	Make community-level analytics (views, downloads) visible to community owners/admins	Low–Med	Open text
10	Enable configurable/customisable automated checks per community, with curator-visible checklist post-publication	Low–Med	Open text

Conclusion

The EOR feedback survey confirms that the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo meets a genuine need and is valued by its user community. 76% use the platform regularly, 78% report improved output visibility, and 55% welcome AI-assisted features - with important caveats around consent and transparency.

The most actionable improvement areas are: (1) reducing friction in metadata entry through DOI/ORCID autofill; (2) improving discoverability through subject/keyword search filters; and (3) communicating the existence of automated checks more prominently. Search engine reliability and author management are recurrent qualitative themes.